

Metal Ion-Ligand Interactions in Thermotropic Liquid Crystals

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Results on the studies of interactions of monovalent metal ions such as Li⁺ and Ag⁺ in LiClO₄, LiBF₄ and AgNO₃ with ligands like acetonitrile, dimethyl sulphoxide, pyridine and acetone in thermotropic liquid crystals are reported. They indicate the formation of metal ion ligand and metal ion-liquid crystal complexes. At least two types of complexes for each metal ion-ligand have been detected. One of these is tetrahedral, providing 'isotropic-like' spectra in the liquid crystalline media.

The area of metal ion-ligand interactions is important both from the chemical and biological points of views. Nuclear magnetic resonance (nmr) has been extensively employed in such work both in isotropic and lyotropic liquid crystalline media¹. The use of nmr in such complexes in media without water is scarce essentially due to solubility reasons. On the other hand, if such complexes are soluble in media like thermotropic liquid crystals, changes in the order parameters and molecular geometries, which are reflected in the spectra, can be detected in such media, leading to reliable information on the complexes²⁻⁵. In this communication, results on lithium and silver ion complexes with acetonitrile, dimethyl sulphoxide, pyridine and acetone and their deuterated analogues are presented. The salts investigated are lithium perchlorate, lithium tetrafluoroborate and silver nitrate and the liquid crystals employed are *N*-(*p*-methoxy/ethoxy)benzylidene)-*p*-*n*-butylaniline (MBBA/EBBA) and their deuterated (*-d*₂) analogues with deuterium substituted at positions *ortho* to the *-N=* group in the butylaniline ring, *trans*, *trans*-4-*n*-propyl-[1,1'-bicyclohexyl]-4'-carbonitrile (ZLI-1184) and *trans*-4-pentyl-1-(4-cyanophenyl)cyclohexane (S-1114).

Results and Discussion

LiClO₄ - ligand solutions: These studies have been undertaken in the liquid crystals MBBA, EBBA and ZLI-1184^{2,4}. The lithium spectra in such solutions without the ligand show 3 : 4 : 3 triplets as expected for spin 3/2 oriented nuclei. The ²H nmr spectra of the solvents MBBA-*d*₂ and EBBA-*d*₂ show two sets of doublets in each case. The larger splittings arise from the quadrupole couplings and the smaller ones (within each component of the quadrupole split doublet) arise essentially from the *ortho* HD-dipolar couplings. Addition of LiClO₄ to these solvents results in the increase of quadrupole and dipolar splittings by

about 10%. This is attributed to the formation of metal ion-liquid crystal complex with nematic liquid crystalline properties.

In order to find the preferential site of complexation, the studies were undertaken in ZLI-1184 which has only one potential complexation site, namely, the cyanide group. The ¹³C-resonance of the cyano-carbon of ZLI-1184 shifts upfield by about 19.5 ppm upon addition of 12.8 mole percent of the salt. The ⁷Li quadrupole splitting decreases from 5950 Hz at 1.5 mole percent salt concentration to 4280 Hz at 12.8 mole percent salt concentration. The results indicate the formation of Li⁺-liquid crystal complex.

¹H and ⁷Li nmr spectra show the coexistence of two types of species in the liquid crystalline solutions containing lithium perchlorate and the ligands soon after the preparation of the solutions. One set of nmr resonances in each spectrum corresponds to the normal oriented species and the other to the 'isotropic-like' form. A phase separation occurs slowly with 'isotropic-like' species settling down in the sample tube. The results can be interpreted in terms of the formation of at least two types of metal ion-ligand complexes - one with tetrahedral symmetry containing 1 : 4 metal ion-ligand molecules and the other containing different ratios of the metal ions to ligands.

LiBF₄ - ligand solutions: Such studies have been undertaken in the liquid crystals S-1114 and S-1184⁴. The salt is practically insoluble in S-1114 indicating that no Li⁺-liquid crystal complex is present in the nematic phase of pure S-1114. However, an addition of about 1.3% by weight of acetonitrile to a mixture of 2.7 mole percent lithium tetrafluoroborate and S-1114 provides a homogeneous solution due to the formation of the metal ion-acetonitrile complex. The proton nmr spectra show a typical triplet as expected for oriented acetonitrile. The triplet separation increases gradually with

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increasing concentration of the salt. For a 7.5 mole percent solution of acetonitrile in the liquid crystal, the increase is about 8% for a solution saturated with LiBF_4 at 20° . The ^7Li and ^{19}F spectra show singlets at all salt concentrations.

By contrast the salt is considerably soluble in ZLI-1184. The results in this case indicate the formation of a liquid crystal complex with the lithium-ions. Since the liquid crystal has a saturated cyclic structure, its only rational site of complexation with lithium ions is the cyano group. The lithium spectra show the usual 3 : 4 : 3 triplet. The ^{19}F spectra are singlets with relatively large line widths due to unresolved dipolar couplings. Addition of acetonitrile to such solutions produces a sharp increase in the intensity of the central component of the triplet in the ^7Li spectra. In addition, the width of the central component increases (to 115 Hz) where as it remains unchanged (50 Hz) for the outer components. The ^{19}F spectra continue to remain singlets without appreciable changes of the width. The proton dipolar couplings of acetonitrile in ZLI-1184 increase upon addition of LiBF_4 . The ^{13}C resonance of the cyano group shifts upfield by about 3 ppm upon addition of the salt to its solubility limit.

The results have been interpreted in terms of the formation of 1 : 4 lithium-acetonitrile tetrahedral complex in S-1114 with practically no distortions in the tetrahedral structure of $[\text{BF}_4]^-$ counter ions. The results in ZLI-1184 can be interpreted in terms of the formation of a Li^+ -liquid crystal complex in addition to the lithium-acetonitrile complex. The lithium ions are found to coordinate preferentially with acetonitrile compared to the liquid crystal (ZLI-1184) cyano group.

AgNO_3 -ligand complexes : These complexes were studied in dried liquid crystals ZLI-1167 and S-1114⁵. In this case too an addition of about 1 weight percent AgNO_3 to a solution of 4 weight percent acetonitrile in ZLI-1167 leads to a separation of the phase into two. The proton nmr spectrum of this mixture contains an additional line near the centre of the triplet due to acetonitrile or an acetonitrile containing species in an 'isotropic-like' environment. Even visually it is the bottom portion which appears 'isotropic-like'. The triplet splitting increases with the increase of concentration of AgNO_3 until the 'isotropic-like' component disappears and a second triplet appears (Fig. 1). A study of the temperature effect on the spectra of the solution exhibiting the two triplets shows that the splitting of the outer triplet decreases more rapidly than that of the inner one, leading to a crossover of the two at nearly 63° . The inner triplet at room temperature corresponds to acetonitrile from the bottom layer. The ^2H spectra of acetonitrile- d_3 under the above conditions are in conformity with the results obtained from the undeuterated species. Optical microscope studies of the individual layers reveal essentially similar textures that appear to be predominantly nematic

Fig. 1. Proton nmr spectra at 270 MHz. The bottom trace is for 1 weight percent silver nitrate in 4 weight percent acetonitrile in ZLI-1167 at 22° . The central and the top traces are for a 12 weight percent silver nitrate solution in 4 weight percent acetonitrile in ZLI-1167 at 22 and 63° respectively.

with another anisotropic phase present in small amounts.

The ^1H and the ^2H nmr spectra of acetonitrile and acetonitrile- d_3 in S-1114 containing AgNO_3 show the appearance of an oriented and an 'isotropic-like' species at all temperatures and concentrations examined. In this case too, a visual phase separation into two layers is observed with bottom portion appearing 'isotropic-like'.

The observation of the 'isotropic-like' components suggests a nonoriented environment. At higher concentrations of silver nitrate in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{AgNO}_3$ - ZLI-1167 solutions the disappearance of the 'isotropic-like' component and the appearance of a second anisotropic component indicate that the silver complex with CH_3CN is present at lower concentrations of AgNO_3 too. The results are interpreted in terms of the formation the tetrahedral as well as non-tetrahedral complexes with the ligands.

Conclusions : The results demonstrate the formation of the metal-ion-ligand as well as the metal-ion liquid crystal complexes. The utility of the study of such weak complexes using nmr is illustrated.

Experimental

About 2–5 weight percent solutions of the ligands were investigated in the dried liquid crystals without the addition of the salts. Solutions were prepared under nitrogen atmosphere in the presence of P_2O_5 in order to minimise contamination by moisture. The 1H spectra were recorded on a WH-270 FT-NMR spectrometer and the 2H , 7Li , ^{13}C and ^{19}F spectra on an MSL-300 instrument. About 100–500 free induction decays were accumulated and Fourier transformed with the help of ASPECT-2000 or ASPECT-3000 computers for WH-270 or MSL-300 spectrometers respectively. Typical spectra are shown in Fig. 1.

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